

EMPLOYMENT SHIFT OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT GRADUATES IN THE POST-PANDEMIC LABOR MARKET

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ABSTRACT

Finding and landing a job related to the degree earned is a challenge faced by most Filipino graduates, many opt to enter a job that is not related to their degree just to make ends meet as one of the reasons. Human Resource Management graduates are not safe from the issue of job mismatch in the country, some have already accepted their fate that they can't land the job they dreamed of, however, many still hope that the perfect job is right around the corner, a page on a book that awaits to be turned. In the advent of the Covid-19 pandemic, job opportunities for Human Resource Management graduates have hindered them maximizing their potential of the degree; several reasons such as lack of job opportunity in the locality, salary rate difference, lack of experience and career change are among the reasons why HR graduates find it difficult to pursue jobs related to their degree. Because of these reasons, this study was conceptualized which analyzes the reasons behind the employment shift of Human Resources Management graduates in the post-pandemic labor market and the incidence of job mismatch among 2021-2022 and 2022-2023 graduates of the degree Bachelor of Business Administration major in Human Resources Management. Graduates of batch 2021-2022 and 2022-2023 were interviewed using a researcher-made questionnaire. Through frequency and percentage statistical tools, the study revealed that a significant number of HR graduates are employed in non-HR-related jobs due to factors such as limited local opportunities, lack of experience, and better offers in other fields. The study points to the importance of increasing partnering between schools and firms, raising the standard of internship courses, and supplying targeted aid for HR careers to close the gap between education and employment.

Keywords: *Human resource management students, job mismatch, post-pandemic, career shift, graduate employability, labor market challenges*

INTRODUCTION

Philippines, a developing country, depends on the labor force as a key player of the factors of production. Majority of its populace are considered capital for the factors of production i.e. as human resource capital or other wisely known as the workforce, in general. According to a statistic published by the Philippine Statistics Authority last November 2024, a 96.8% employment rate was recorded and the Department of Finance in February 2025, accounted a total of 48.8 million Filipinos as employed on that same year. However, there exists a pressing issue behind these promising statistics--- job mismatch.

While the numbers above are promising, it can be noted that it fails however to present whether or not this employed individuals are practicing the job in lined with their profession. Job mismatch is a phenomenon where educated workers enter a job which they are not trained for (Medina, 2015). For example, a licensed professional teacher working graveyard shifts on a BPO company and/or an engineer by profession that works as an unskilled laborer in a construction site. Studies further claimed that majority of college graduates in the country are underutilized in the employment market (Medina, 2015) and that Filipino nurses experience job mismatch in their chosen fields (Condes and Lachica, 2022).

Filipino college graduates find difficulty in securing jobs aligned with their skills (O'Connor, 2025), among them are the graduates of Human Resource Management of Mariano Marcos State University. Several graduates of the program are experiencing job mismatch from several factors such as i) few job opportunities in the locality, ii) lack of skills required by the profession, iii) unfavorable working conditions, iv) salary, v) other job opportunities to meet needs, vi) personal reasons and vii) the Covid-19 pandemic. The promising future of the graduates is hindered due to the factors mentioned above. They are oftentimes forced to work on jobs not related to their profession just to make ends meet and/or to avoid the stigma of unemployment posed by the all-seeing eyes of the criticism of societal expectations. This leads them to a take-it-or-leave-it dilemma which, eventually, further contributes to job mismatch, hence this study.

Studying the factors that led to job mismatch among HR graduates helps educational institutions, especially HEIs, to identify the pressing needs of their students to cope up with the dynamic needs of education most specifically in the curriculum and employment standards globally. This study also serves as a guide among the graduates of HR to further analyze the importance of practicing their profession as one of the indicators of economic progress and personal and professional development.

Thus, this study is conceptualized to identify the factors that led to job mismatch of MMSU HR graduates of the post-pandemic era specifically the graduates of the

program of 2021-2022 and 2022-2023. It further explores the jobs where the respondents landed after graduation and their current employment to elaborate the relationship of the factors that lead to job mismatch to their current workstations.

Research Questions

This study aimed on identifying the factors that led to job mismatch among HR graduates of Mariano Marcos State University and their current workstations, specifically of years 2022-2023.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions?

1. What are the jobs landed on by HR graduates after graduation?
2. Is their current employment in line with their profession?
3. What are the factors that led to the employment shift among the respondents in the post-pandemic labor market?

Literature Review

Employment Opportunities for HR Graduates

The employment scenario for human resource management graduates has certainly transformed drastically with the associations of new technology and change in the organizational structure of post COVID-19. DeLisi (2020) noted that as workplaces now experience digital transformation, HR professionals with skills in HR information systems (HRIS), data analytics and virtual talent management will be in great demand. These changes have brought more employment opportunities within HR role itself but also beyond the HR role into HR technology, remote workforce management and organizational development.

Furthermore, Jackson et al. (2014), points out that strategic HRM is becoming more important for contemporary businesses. With an increasing number of companies looking for HR professionals who can help them achieve long-term business goals, a growing trend of combining HR functions with the overall business strategy is being seen. The presence of this strategic perspective evolves advanced roles for HR graduates, namely the HR business partners, the talent strategist, and the organizational consultant.

In the Philippines, hence, Villanueva & Valerio (2019) underscored that there are many employability opportunities for HR graduates which, however, depend on matching the HR training exposure to the industry needs. The ones who get placements after six months from graduation are those who have experience of internships, they got communication skills, and they are tech savvy.

Despite the job opportunities available for HR graduates, their employability was affected greatly by the onset of the Covid-19 pandemic. Several business establishments opted to cut the number of their employees into order to keep their business going which resulted in the unemployment of those unfortunate employees who were removed. In the

educational aspect, the delivery of the teaching-learning process shifted to online or modular mode where, instead of the conventional face-to-face classes, the teaching-learning process became more of a written tasks performance which hindered learning and the acquiring of the necessary skills for HR students and graduates that are critical in their field of specialization.

Thus, the pandemic adversely affected graduates' ability to work efficiently when they get to the workforce. It was revealed in the study of Kamaruddin et al. (2023) that the students that were taught remotely found it difficult to acquire practical skills and were therefore headed for failure in employment.

Job Mismatch Among HR Graduates

Alsadi et. al. (2019) conducted a study on the employment issues of human resource management (HRM) graduates, particularly those in Ghana, and discovered that even with the surge in the number of HRM programs, graduates could not find their way into HRM careers. The main problem arising is the absence of HR positions inside the organizations, in which there are fewer HR departments, usually one manager and one assistant, this implies that there are no places for new graduates. The study also discussed the discrepancy between what's taught in the curriculum and the actual requirement of the industry leading to graduates who are insufficiently equipped for the real HR functions.

Moreover, the report by Suryadarma et al. (2020), in Indonesia, 53 % of college graduates got employment in unconfined employment that did not require a degree. In the education sector, the graduates were often to be seen undertaking jobs in small enterprises and call centers whilst business graduates found themselves on job positions like ride-share drivers or retail. Here, the results are like those of the Philippines, where there exists a great surplus of labor and limited scope for job growth at a regional level. Nowadays, employment mismatch can be considered as one of the major concerns of the Philippine economy. Thus, one of the factors that can be attributed to this is that students want to pursue a college degree that is relevant in the current job market since they end up with a degree that is not in high demand in the Philippine market (Chonco, 2023).

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED, 2021) reveals that close to 35% of the graduates in universities in the Philippines get jobs outside their area of specialization. Specifically, a large pool of engineering graduates finds jobs as technical support agents in BPO organizations without those opportunities to utilize their engineering qualifications. Accountancy and finance graduates find themselves working in areas such as logistics coordination or marketing in most cases by virtue of scarcity of junior jobs within accounting or financial firms.

Many IT graduates are employed in clerical or sales jobs, mainly according to Asian Development Bank research conducted in 2020. It demonstrated that around the world digital skills are in high demand. This finding indicates the deficiencies in more than just

the course content itself—specifically, the way in which university programs fail to prepare graduates for the skills that employers claim to require.

In tourism and hospitality management, graduates, especially those who were hit by the COVID-19 pandemic, found themselves being employed as warehouse assistants, online sellers, or as ordinary office staff as some of the hotels and travel agencies downsized their workforce or wound up their operations (DOLE, 2021). Aligning with a 2022 DOLE report, about 25% of registered nurses work in call centers or factories as production workers because there are few job openings in hospitals and health agencies. Business oriented courses also suffer similar imbalances apart from the health and the education sector. Graduation from HRM often ends up in sales, clerical or administrative posts, without a chance to perform normal HR roles. Drawing the results from PIDS (2020), graduates of business who majored in HR ended up as field representatives, for motorcycle dealerships or in positions as the clerical staff in the local government office without any room to implement the HR skills they acquired.

In the study of Bayudan-Dacuycuy & Dacuycuy (2018), the people of highest risks of mismatches in terms of their employment were the HR and social science graduates concerned with Northern Luzon. Rather than pursuing careers in organizational HR positions, many found themselves in barangay offices or involved as enumerators in projects funded by government censuses. Inadequate collaboration among provincial academic institutions and industries led to the job mismatch.

Manasan (2020), from Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS), says that the problem is not just unemployment, but also underemployment, as many graduates are only employed due to the basic high school skills required. The report cited examples such as psychology graduates working as online sellers and HRM graduates taking jobs as delivery riders or store cashiers.

Chonco (2023) states that our current educational system should endeavor to advise senior high school leavers to take the correct decision towards choosing their preferred college degree. In the same work, Chonco (2023) encourages the students to acquire high return skills which do not require a college degree. This practice will reduce the time to be taken by serving as a useful guide to calculate the return of investment and be a direct blessing to the learners in the enhancement of their skills.

Determinants of Job Mismatch

The problem of job mismatch is a global undertaking, countries around the world experience this issue. Job mismatch continues to be a perennial problem for new graduates in the Philippines. The PIDS reports that many, like those in Human Resource Management (HRM), find themselves filling positions which are technically outside their areas of academic specialization. There are various reasons why there is such a mismatch, and these include an excess of students enrolled in business-related degree programs, disconnect from the theoretical classroom to the requirements of industry, and the hiring preferences of employers for those who already have some relevant work

experience. Graduates with an HRM background, as a result, may end up in jobs such as sales agents, call center representatives, or administrative assistant's jobs, which are not a reflection of their material gained in human resources studies.

The high rate of development in Indian higher education, which exceeds the establishment of suitable job, leads to a wide job mismatch. As reported in the India Skills Report, many Indian graduates do well theoretically but fail to gain some practical skills that are needed in the employers' firms. Therefore, many graduates land in posts that are not required by their qualification or belong outside their area of academic specialty. Such a lack of alignment is aggravated by the lack of systemized intern programs, and a lack of industry educational partnerships.

In the United States, high job mismatch is much attributed to the impact of technological disruption and automation. Automation of tasks people used to perform manually or with the help of routine procedures has led to shifts in the workforce as employees are being pushed outside their roles and jobs incompatible with their educational background. The Center on Education and the Workforce, at Georgetown University, reports a significant percentage of college grads working in jobs that non-college-educated workers could fill. Such underemployment represents a vertical mismatch with overqualified employees in positions.

Additionally, Holidi & Abu Seman (2023), a study in Malaysia discovered that ill employability skills possessed by graduates like communication, problem-solving and adaptability also play a very critical role in job mismatches and unemployment. And as a result, employers frequently struggle to find candidates who are compatible with their organization needs, highlighting the need to make the academic curricula compatible with industry needs.

Job mismatch has been a long issue in the Philippines, there are studies from the past that has already identified the determinants of job mismatch however, there is yet an action from the Philippine government to address these issues. As stated in the study of (Condes & Lachica, 2022), it is an interesting phenomenon that is especially endemic to registered nurses in the Philippines, who have more than 200,000 professionals working as non-healthcare personnel because of reasons like low wage compensation, lack of career paths, and harsh working conditions. However, such mismatches not only affect individuals' job satisfaction and performance but also have a macroeconomic implication. According to the study conducted in 2019 by Reyes, C.M., Tabuga, A.D., and Minca, C. D., graduates are frequently lacking specific technical skills expected from the industry which requires them to apply for positions outside the field of study. Many business /HR graduates find themselves employed in clerical or sales capacities and under employed. The study of Guzman and Castro (2021) revealed that job mismatches are experienced when the college curricula do not include on-the-job practical experience or real workplace exposure. It showed that many HR graduates end up in customer-facing service roles that are largely due to interning that was not substantial.

Based on the result of Cruz, R.S. (2020) investigation into businesses and HRM graduates within Luzon, he found that selection criteria employers significantly raise the possibility of job inappropriateness. Reasonably, employers pursue experienced individuals for entry jobs which means many fresh graduates find themselves working in retail or government ventures (like GIP) or even informal occupations when they are more than qualified for better fit work.

Post-Pandemic Employment Shift

COVID 19 pandemic has greatly modified the employment scene in the Philippines with subsequent shifts in the dynamics of its workforce and HR practices. A marked change, however, comes in the form of remote and hybrid work models being adopted by various workplaces. In an article published by Crismundo (2023) citing result of the study of Universum Talent Survey from 2022-2023, legitimate organization used by companies and universities to understand shifts in the job market, it showed that 82% of the Filipino Gen Z students were interested in companies that are offering hybrid work arrangements which means, showing more preference for flexibility in workplace.

However, the fresh graduates, largely those that are virtual learning students, find it difficult to get employment. These graduates usually graduate without the practical skills and the experience to compete with established professionals coming back from the labor market, Employers Confederation of the Philippines (ECOP) said.

In the article published by Subingsubing and Piad (2023) for the Inquirer.net, it affirmed the statement of the Commission on Human Rights (CHR) that graduates from the pandemic era did not develop critical soft skills, which are now no longer adequate for employers: collaboration, problem-solving, and adaptability. A case is where a graduate in HR was allocated as a field representative for a motorcycle company, which has no relation to HR management type jobs. Such a situation is normally due to the narrow HR employment opportunities or the belief that other HR jobs are more readily available.

A study revealed that some of the Human Resource Management graduates in the Philippines are working in non-related jobs to what they were specialized to learn. This difference is in part since there are comparatively too few HR jobs, so graduates tend to work in unrelated careers simply to accrue some practical experience. For example, human resource specialists should be potentially employed in sales, administrative or customer service departments where they are not usually putting into use their HR training.

The Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS) reported that an approximate 40% of Filipino workers work within their educational qualifications as requirements for their jobs. Such overqualification causes people to find themselves in completely irrelevant work positions, and this creates horizontal mismatches. For example, a graduate with an HR degree may find themselves in a position of being a

salesperson thus showing a wrong match between qualification and the prevailing duties of a job.

It has also been an occasion for companies to capitalize on new opportunities to employ talents based in locations outside of Metro Manila. Hybrid work models have been implemented well by the PLDT and GCash to make it possible for them to hire well-skilled professionals from different provinces and thus promote regional development. The positive effects of decentralization on regional economies have been eclipsed by the problems faced by freshly graduated students from non-urban universities in larger, more competitive labor markets, with increased focus on employability and technical knowledge required.

The Philippine labor market was greatly disrupted by the COVID-19 pandemic, resulting in considerable shifts in employment behavior. In 2020, a study from the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS) shows that the average annual hours worked dropped from 2,189 hours (2012-2019) to 1,891 hours, equivalent to loss of approximately two month's full-time work. Adjustments to existing work schedules were largely the cause of this reduction, which would suggest a change in the number of people working away rather than the number of jobs available.

Sprout Solutions also witnessed a significant rise in voluntary resignation during the pandemic decades of 176%. Workers disengaged from their current work and instead joined remote-friendly jobs or career changes that expanded growth in less traditional-skilled industries and aggravated skill shortages among new market hands.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed descriptive quantitative research design using a survey questionnaire as an instrument for data gathering. The researcher utilized purposive sampling techniques in selecting participants in this study. The researcher prepared a self-made questionnaire validated by experts. A total of fifty (50) graduates responded on the survey conducted, all of which are graduates of Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Human Resource Management of Mariano Marcos State University of the school years 2021-2022 and 2022-2023.

The data gathered regarding the respondents' previous and current workstations were categorized based on whether the jobs were related or unrelated to their HR degree. These categories were then tallied using frequency counts to identify the number of respondents who experienced employment shifts. Percentages were computed to show the proportion of those who shifted to jobs outside their field versus those who remained in HR-related roles. This treatment allowed the researcher to determine the incidence and extent of job mismatch among the respondents.

Data was gathered through online questionnaires distributed through social media platforms. All protocols for data privacy were observed to ensure research ethics during the data gathering procedure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the study are as follows:

Table 1. Demographic profile of the respondents (N=50)

Profile	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
Year Graduated		
2021-2022	15	30.00
2022-2023	35	70.00

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents by their year of graduation. Of the fifty (50) respondents, about 35 or 70% were graduates of the 2022-2023 academic year. Fifteen (15) respondents (30%) in comparison, graduated in the academic year 2021-2022. Because of this, the data gives good insights into what has been happening for more current graduates. The higher representation from the 2022-2023 group may suggest a stronger relevance of current employment trends and job market conditions among the participants.

Table 2. Employment status of HR graduates immediately after graduation

Profile	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
Response		
Yes	16	32.00
No	34	68.00

Table 2 presents the employment status of HR graduates immediately after graduation. According to the survey, sixteen (16) of the 50 respondents (32%) started work in Human Resources right after graduation. However, 68% of the respondents, 34 in total, said they were unable to find employment in the HR field directly after finishing their degree. These numbers show that a large group of HR graduates have trouble finding employment in their area of study once they begin working. The results point to the possibility that not many HR graduates find suitable work in the field right away.

Table 3. Previous Job Positions Held by Respondents After Graduation

Profile	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
Response		
HR related jobs	14	28.00
Non-HR related jobs	36	72.00

Table 3 gives out previous job positions held by the respondents after graduation by the following set out classification with respect to their Human Resource (HR) degree. The data show that only 14 of the 50 respondents (28%) managed to get jobs as HR-related jobs after graduation. On the other hand, a very high number, 36 respondents (72%) had non-HR employment. This shows a significant trend towards job-role mismatch among the HR graduates; most of them are taking up fields outside their academic field of specialization. The results can be due to a lack of opportunities for HR job, regional labor market constraints or the desire for immediate employment irrespective of a field. Such findings emphasize the need for career guidance and early exposure to HR practice in addition to responsive job market strategies to help graduates get jobs in line with their qualifications.

Table 4. Current employment alignment of respondents with their HR degree

Profile	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
Response		
Yes	21	42.00
No	29	58.00

Table 4 shows the alignment between respondents' current work and their Human Resource Management degree. Twenty-one or 42% of the 50 respondents, said they have jobs that fit with their HR degree now. In contrast, 29 respondents or 58% said they are working in jobs not closely linked to their academic training. It appears from the results that HR graduates still experience job mismatches, as most participants are employed in fields outside their area of study. As a result, it indicates that industry-academe partnerships and supportive mechanisms matter for better graduate job opportunities in their selected disciplines.

Table 5. Reasons HR Graduates Seek Non-HR Jobs in the Post-Pandemic Market

Profile	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
Reasons		
Personal Preference or change in career interest	23	46.00
Higher Salary or better benefits offered in another field.	27	54.00
Lack of required experience or qualifications in the HR field	23	46.00
Limited job opportunities related to Human Resource Management	43	86.00
Influence of family or peer decisions in choosing a different job	10	20.00
To work as Overseas Foreign Workers	1	2.00
Influence of job market trends	1	2.00

Table 5 shows the main reasons cited by HR graduates for getting jobs outside their area of specialization after the pandemic. According to most respondents, or 86% of them, the scarcity of Human Resource Management jobs stands out as the main reason. This reveals that there are not enough HR-specialized jobs, so graduates must find work elsewhere. Besides, the choice of higher salary or better benefits in other fields was selected by 27 respondents (54%), making economic factors an important reason for job mismatch. Personal career preferences or shifts and shortages in HR-specific qualifications were each chosen by 23 respondents (46%), suggesting that personal aims as well as skills expectations play a role. Reasons such as being influenced by family or peers were chosen by 20%, while 2% each chose to work as Overseas Foreign Workers, follow market trends, or work at places with more opportunities. The results seem to indicate that job mismatches are mainly caused by economic and structural factors, but personal and social reasons also play some part though.

Conclusions

The research work on the Employment Shift of HR Graduates in the Post-Pandemic Labor Market showed a great divergence from the classical notions of career orientation in HR graduates. Findings reported that a significant percentage (68%) of respondents did not get immediately jobs in HR after graduation, while most (72%) were in non-HR jobs in their initial jobs. Before getting into the details of the financial hardship, it must be noted that even now only 58% are working in occupations connected with their degree, which further describes a continuing trend for career displacement.

Overall, the findings show how the post-pandemic labor market affected HR graduates to change and vary their profession paths. The change describes limitations of the current labor market as well as students' flexibility in the context of their relationship to the labor market. Considering this, institutions, employers, and graduates should join forces to establish better career services, improve matching skills, and generate more HR positions in both the local and global job sectors.

Recommendations

Based on the result of the study, the following are the recommendations of the researchers:

First, HR students/graduates are recommended to look up to HR as a respected profession and not only as a degree to accomplish. Graduates must seek employment related to HR as it will help them realize their degree and chosen profession. HR also offers promising job opportunities not only in the country but also abroad thus, it is recommended that graduates apply their degree after graduation to avoid job mismatch.

Second, educational institutions should partner with the industry for practicum placements, seminars and mentorship openings to allow students more opportunities to

apply their knowledge and skills in real-life situations. The teaching-learning process should be directed towards the attainment of the core values and/or competencies expected from the graduates. Also, the educational curriculum should be assessed from time to time to cope with the changes brought by modernization and globalization. Additionally, to improve and assure post-graduate employment of the HR graduates in the post-pandemic labor market, it is advisable for the academic institutions to improve the student internships and incorporations of the career readiness preparations to enable the students to gauge better with the HR careers.

Third, government agencies, especially the Department of Labor and Employment, must take a more active part in promoting HR to make the field more promising and strategic. DOLE can support the formation of job sites for HR professionals and offer labor market data to help guide both students and jobseekers. The department must provide skills development courses and certifications with TESDA and approved training organizations, especially in areas such as digital systems, recruitment, and labor laws that are required in HR. The development of strong ties between colleges and companies for internships and apprenticeships to gain useful experience.

And lastly, researchers can utilize this study to better understand the kinds of trends and problems HR graduates face in the current job market. It may act as the foundation for succeeding studies of skills gaps, graduate job success, and HR careers. This research's identification of problems and proposed solutions can push for more studies focused on advancing education, matching skills to jobs, and enhancing HR and related policy making.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers made sure to always behave ethically during the study. Participants provided their consent only after they were informed of what the study involved. All participants' identities were protected, so no information that could identify them was released. All the researchers declared that there was no conflict of interest during the study. Pledges to avoid plagiarism were kept, while all sources were properly cited. Also, the data were analyzed fairly, without any bias, and the results were applied only for research and academic reasons.

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